

Preliminary Characterization of the Multorpor Mountain Fault: Tectonic Implications for the Mount Hood Fault Zone, north-central Oregon

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ABSTRACT

The Mount Hood fault zone in north-central Oregon is a ~55 km-long, north-trending zone of active faulting along the western margin of the Hood River graben. The fault zone was discovered after reviewing high-resolution light detection and ranging data (LiDAR) of the surrounding area and includes several fault segments such as the Multorpor Mountain fault. The role that these segments play in accommodating Cascade intra-arc extension and regional crustal rotation remains poorly constrained and their slip rate and recency of activity are not understood. Using LiDAR data, we identified fault scarps and extracted topographic profiles across suspected fault traces. Using MATLAB we measured and analyzed vertical offsets that ranged between 1 to 72 meters. These displacements were then ranked based on the quality and confidence of the correlative geomorphic surface offset across the fault. These observations cumulatively suggest several surface-rupturing earthquakes have occurred on the Multorpor Mountain fault during late Quaternary time. Surface rupturing earthquakes on the 12 km long Multorpor Mountain fault could result in up to a 6.3 M earthquake, using empirical fault-scaling relationships. Our findings for the Multorpor Mountain fault segment of the Mount Hood fault zone contribute to improved understanding of displacement along strike, fault characterization, and seismic hazard assessment, offering new insight into how extensional strain is partitioned along active faults in the Cascade arc.

INTRODUCTION

Oregon lies east of the Cascadia Subduction Zone, where the Juan de Fuca plate is subducting underneath the North America plate, and north of the San Andreas transform fault. These major tectonic boundaries contribute to the active tectonics of the Cascadia region and drive the clockwise rotational movement of the overriding North America plate (Wells & McCaffrey, 2013). In recent decades, faults have been identified within the region of Mount Hood, including the Multorpor Mountain fault of the Mount Hood fault zone (Madin et al., 2021). This discovery adds to the growing recognition of the region's seismic potential. By analyzing empirical fault-scaling relationships, we can estimate the number and magnitude of earthquakes responsible for the observed surface displacements (Wells & Coppersmith, 1994). These relationships are essential for evaluating seismic hazard in complex tectonic settings like the Cascade Range. Despite the region's tectonic activity, the seismic history and potential of active faults in the Mount Hood area remain poorly constrained. In particular, it is unclear how many earthquakes have contributed to the fault scarps

observed in the region. This study focuses on the Multorpor Mountain fault to estimate the number and magnitude of past surface rupturing earthquakes to improve our understanding of future seismic risk.

BACKGROUND

Clockwise rotation of the Cascade arc is occurring at a rate of $1.0^\circ/\text{y.r.}$, accommodating regional crustal deformation (Wells and McCaffrey, 2013). This tectonic movement contributes to extensional strain and northwest translation of crustal blocks in the Mount Hood region by surface faulting (Madin et al., 2021). The Mount Hood fault zone (Fig. 1) was discovered using high-resolution LiDAR data collected by the Oregon Department of Geology and Mineral Industries (DOGAMI). Within this zone, the Multorpor Mountain fault, an east-dipping normal fault, and the west-dipping Twin Lakes fault define the margins of a graben structure (Madin et al., 2017). Seismic data recorded between 1986 until 2002 reveal earthquake clusters with hypocentral depths of 3.5-4.5 km, distinguishing them from typical volcanic seismicity (Jones and Malone, 2005), which suggests that faults near Mount Hood are currently active. This study provides preliminary data for the Multorpor Mountain fault that will help future studies on determining slip rates. Determining fault activity in this area is vital for the city of Government Camp, nearby critical infrastructure, as well as recreational activity for the area of Mount Hood. My goal is to provide foundational data on surface displacement, confidence in the measurements, and lidar based geomorphic evaluation of near-fault deposits to support future field investigations of this potentially active fault system.

Figure 1. Mount Hood fault zone with fault scarps (red lines) mapped by Madin et al. (2021). The yellow box outlines the location of the Multorpor Mountain fault shown in Figure 2.

METHODS

My approach involves using high-resolution LiDAR mapping to analyze the Multorpor Mountain area for fault scarps, or geomorphic evidence of faulting. I extracted topographic profiles across suspected fault traces and processed the elevation data in MATLAB to quantify vertical offsets. To refine the mapping of fault scarps along the Multorpor Mountain fault, I reviewed previous fault mapping (Madin et al., 2021; Madin & Ma, 2012) along with LiDAR topographic data from the Oregon Lidar Consortium (2009, 2015) in ArcGIS Pro software. I created hillshade derivatives of the LiDAR data in ArcGIS Pro with sun-angle azimuths of 45°, 315°, and 225° to enhance surface visualization. Fault scarps and landslides were then mapped based on contour lines and topographic surface expression observed in the hillshades (Fig. 2). To understand the local geology along the fault, I added ArcGIS files of map units (polygons) and contacts and faults (polylines) to my map that were derived from a 60-minute quadrangle geologic map (Ma et al., 2014; Sherrod and Scott, 1995). Topographic profiles across the scarps were extracted (Fig. 3, Appendix) and exported as CSV files, which were then imported into MATLAB. In this study, we apply Monte Carlo methods outlined in Thompson et al., (2002), to characterize fault slip of the Multorpor Mountain fault, a critical step in assessing seismic hazard and advancing our understanding of the Mount Hood fault zone. SlipMC code (Duckworth et al., 2021), a MATLAB code which uses Monte Carlo simulation, implements the probabilistic treatment of uncertainties in vertical slip, fault dip, and surface age, all of which influence net slip calculations as outlined in Thompson et al. (2002). The output included tables of statistical slip values and standard deviations for each scarp profile (Appendix). In ArcGIS Pro, I measured the distance of each scarp profile from the southern end of the Multorpor Mountain fault, which was compiled with slip data from MATLAB. This dataset was then imported into RStudio to generate a slip distribution plot (Fig. 4b). Regression lines were used to characterize spatial trends in slip along the fault (Fig. 4c). Following the initial data collection phase, field reconnaissance was conducted to validate and contextualize initial interpretations.

Figure 2. (top) Geologic map of the Mount Hood 30-by-60-minute quadrangle, showing map units from Ma et al. (2014). This map is based on the preliminary geologic map of the area and displays units covering Oligocene to Quaternary age. (bottom) Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) hillshade map of the Multorpor Mountain fault using a 315° azimuth illumination. Fault scarp traces are shown in red, and profile lines used for offset measurements are shown in black. The yellow box indicates the area enlarged in Figure 3.

RESULTS

Fault Scarp Mapping

Lidar analysis reveals that the Multorpor Mountain fault is an east-dipping normal fault with a ~12 km-long surface expression. Multiple distinct fault strands exhibit topographic scarps in LiDAR topographic data. Offset measurements at 27 topographic profiles across the fault scarps range from 1.1 to 72.4 meters (Appendix). For each topographic profile, we use SlipMC tool (Duckworth et al., 2021) to generate a graph that shows vertical slip of a geomorphic surface that I interpret to have been previously correlative but was subsequently offset by normal faulting. For example, profile 12 (Fig. 3b) shows 10.96 m of vertical slip of a basaltic geomorphic surface. Across a small right step in the fault trace, profile 13a (Fig. 3c) shows a small graben with 17.1 m of east-down vertical slip across the primary, east-dipping fault (Fig. 3d) and 5.22 m of west-down vertical slip across an antithetic, west-dipping fault. Thus, total offset across the graben is interpreted as 11.88 meters of east-down vertical slip.

Figure 3. (a) LiDAR hillshade with 315° azimuth illumination, showing a zoomed-in view of topographic profiles 11 to 14 along the Multorpor Mountain fault. (b) Topographic profile 12, with a mean vertical slip of 10.96 m. (c) Topographic profile 13a, showing a mean vertical slip of 17.1 m across the primary, east-dipping fault. (d) Topographic profile 13b, showing a mean vertical slip of 5.22 m across a secondary, west-dipping antithetic fault.

Quantifying Confidence in Fault Scarp Offset

To quantify the confidence in my geomorphic interpretation of faulting, and the resultant estimates of fault slip, I created a ranking system based on two criteria. First, ground surface correlation between the upthrown and downthrown surface of each profile was given a rank from confident (3), probable (2), and questionable (1). Second, the length of the scarp was given a rank from >1 km (3), 500 to 999 m (2), and <500 m (1). Each profile received a combined score ranging between 2 to 6 by summing the two criteria (Table 1). Profiles with higher total scores are interpreted as having greater geomorphic and structural confidence. Based

on these evaluations, the highest confidence profiles are 3, 5, 12, 13, 26, and 27. The purpose of the ranking table was to identify the most reliable fault scarps for potential future paleoseismic trenching and to distinguish true tectonic scarps from less certain geomorphic features. This process strengthened my observations by helping to identify scarps that exhibit clear, continuous surface correlations across the fault, an essential criterion for applying the Monte Carlo analysis. Additionally, it helped confirm which scarps are geometrically consistent and collinear along strike, improving confidence in their tectonic origin and continuity from north to south.

Table 1. Fault Scarp Confidence Summary. The table also includes the distance of each profile from the southern end of the Mulptopor Mountain fault. These values help identify the most reliable scarps for detailed analysis and potential paleoseismic trenching.

Profile	Fault trace Length (m)	Distance From South	Criteria 1 Ground Surface match	Criteria 2 Continuity	Sum of Criteria 1 and 2
1	388	1188	3	1	4
2	388	1171	3	1	4
3	1381	1134	3	3	6
4	1381	1086	2	3	5
5	1381	1050	3	3	6
6	335	1002	2	1	3
7	335	9910	2	1	3
8	1672	9980	2	3	5
9w	513	9598	3	2	5
9c	89	9598	3	1	4
9e	194	9598	3	1	4
10	513	9300	2	2	4
11	156	8981	2	1	3
12	1672	8461	3	3	6
13	705,593	8295	3	3	6
14	705,593	7947	3	2	5
15	318	7578	3	1	4
16	567	5034	3	2	5
17	567	4757	3	2	5
18	493	4570	2	1	3
19	858	4201	3	2	5
20	858	3984	2	2	4
21	648	3538	2	2	4
22	698	2444	1	2	3
23	698	2011	2	2	4
24	713	1033	1	2	3
25	713	730	1	2	3
26	1131	607	3	3	6
27	1131	159	3	3	6
			3 = confident	3 = longest (>1km)	
	total:	1197	2 = probable	2 = 500m<distance<1km	
			1 = questionable	1 = <500m	

Fault Scarp Offset Characterization

To characterize spatial variations in slip, a slip distribution plot was generated (Fig. 4b). Logarithmic and quadratic regression models were applied (Fig. 4c), but neither adequately matched the observed pattern. As an alternative a non-parametric regression line (LOESS) was also used, which more closely reflects the overall distribution of slip observations along the fault. These regression curves are interpreted to represent the cumulative surface ruptures produced by an unknown number of past surface-rupturing earthquakes. Variations in earthquake magnitude, fault segmentation, or recurrence during several past earthquakes likely influences the observed variations in the cumulative fault slip values along the Multorpor Mountain fault. Using scaling relationships from Wells and Coppersmith (1994), a fault length of 12 kilometers corresponds to an estimated moment magnitude (M_w) of 6.3. This value is consistent with typical magnitude-length regressions for normal faulting events. However, fault scarp morphology and displacement provide additional insight into the rupture history. When interpreted using a slip-based magnitude scaling (Wells & Coppersmith, 1994), the slip observations could indicate a single larger magnitude event or multiple surface-rupturing earthquakes with relatively smaller slip values. In particular, vertical offsets greater than 1-2 meters observed on the Multorpor Mountain likely reflect a complex rupture history involving cumulative displacement from multiple surface-rupturing earthquakes, rather than a single event. For example, scarps with evidence for up to ~25 m of slip may represent a dozen or more surface-rupturing late Quaternary earthquakes (Fig. 4b). One outlier with ~72 m of slip (profile 14) may record longer-term repeated fault offset of volcanic bedrock over hundreds of thousands to millions of years. These interpretations highlight the potential for recurrent fault activity on the Multorpor Mountain fault and underscore the importance of integrating both geomorphic and empirical approaches in seismic hazard assessments.

Figure 4. (a) Multorpor Mountain fault strip map with topographic scarps (red), profiles (black), and landslides in blue. (b) Slip Distribution along the Multorpor Mountain fault based on vertical offset measurements from 27 topographic profiles. The number of surface-rupturing earthquakes (yellow bars and red text) are inferred using empirical displacement relationships for normal faults from Wells & Coppersmith (1994). Variations in slip may reflect multiple rupture events, fault segmentation, or differences in rupture propagation. (c) Slip distribution along the Multorpor Mountain fault fit with regression line models to evaluate spatial variability in vertical offset. Logarithmic and quadratic regressions were applied but did not adequately capture observed trends. A non-parametric LOESS (Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing) regression provided a better fit, highlighting localized variations in slip that may reflect differences in rupture behavior, fault segmentation, or recurrence history.

Geologic Displacements

Observations from the geologic map by Ma et al. (2014) (Fig 2) indicate that the Multorpor Mountain fault primarily displaces unconsolidated Quaternary deposits, including glacial till, colluvial, alluvial, as well as andesitic lava flows. The displacement of both surficial sediments and older volcanic units suggests a history of recurrent fault activity that spans multiple depositional and eruptive episodes. The presence of faulted Quaternary materials implies that the most recent surface rupture likely occurred during the late Pleistocene or Holocene, reinforcing the potential for future seismic activity.

DISCUSSION

This study provides insights into the geometry and slip behavior of the Multorpor Mountain fault, an east-dipping normal fault that is part of the Mount Hood fault zone and bounds the western margin of a graben structure (Madin et al., 2017; 2021). A notable limitation of this research is the presence of extensive landslide deposits that obscure portions of the fault trace, complicating the interpretation of surface offsets (Fig. 2). Future work should prioritize characterizing landslide processes to distinguish between tectonic and gravitational origins (Baroň et al., 2024). In the summer of 2025, a paleoseismic trench was excavated to the south in the Oak Grove Graben (see Fig. 1 for location). Given the spatial proximity, similar north-south orientation, and co-linear nature of the scarps associated with both the Oak Grove Graben and Multorpor Mountain fault, their potential structural linkage is highly possible and of significant interest. Future studies should investigate whether these faults have experienced synchronous rupture events or influence each other's slip behavior through structural interactions in transfer zones (Gawthorpe & Hurst, 1993). According to criteria based on table 1, scarp from profile 27 would be a good candidate for a future trench site to evaluate this fault connectivity. As the relationships between fault activity and surface processes become clearer, future research will be essential in resolving the kinematic evolution of the Mount Hood fault zone.

CONCLUSIONS

These findings enhance our understanding of tectonic deformation near Mount Hood, OR and carry important implications for regional seismic hazard assessment. Observed vertical scarp slip of up to 72 meters along the Multorpor Mountain fault suggest significant cumulative slip, supporting its classification as an active, structurally significant fault with a history of repetitive surface-rupturing earthquakes in the Quaternary. Future research, such as a paleoseismic trenching, should aim to better constrain recurrence intervals and evaluate the potential for fault interaction within the Mount Hood fault zone and adjacent fault systems, especially the adjacent Oak Grove Graben. Such work will contribute to the development of more accurate seismic risk models for the region. Given the proximity of the Multorpor Mountain fault to the town of Government Camp, OR and the greater Portland-Vancouver metropolitan region, assessing the slip rate of this fault is important for understanding the seismic threat to nearby communities.

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Appendix of Profiles

11

12

13a

13b

14a

14b

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ProfileName	VSepMean	VSepMedian	VSepMode	VSepRange	VSepStandDev	VSepUpperCI	VSepLowerCI	SlipMean	SlipMedian	SlipMode	SlipRange	SlipStandDev	SlipUpperCI	SlipLowerCI
1	1.08912414	1.08809177	1.11	0.46213639	0.07250219	1.236	0.943	1.17507251	1.17326389	1.2	0.54492952	0.08644619	1.357	1.007
2	1.62148245	1.61839838	1.6	1.13401806	0.19025805	2.013	1.235	1.68658478	1.67998605	1.7	1.21899018	0.20166799	2.1	1.278
3	3.51917126	3.51842903	3.54	0.50931109	0.07283277	3.668	3.377	3.59571305	3.59102595	3.57	0.64025778	0.09542787	3.789	3.41
3_B	1.18780921	1.18268449	1.2	2.05760678	0.26277927	1.732	0.667	1.22300928	1.22371318	1.3	2.13230301	0.27180957	1.789	0.682
4	12.4037287	12.4090893	12.5	1.75899239	0.26163169	12.927	11.868	13.1222056	13.0920075	13	2.90682923	0.43566256	14.037	12.303
5	1.44016439	1.44192148	1.5	0.79096377	0.11453234	1.669	1.208	1.55009348	1.55275034	1.65	0.88392515	0.13142189	1.821	1.285
6	10.1700927	10.165423	9.8	2.38601474	0.52264957	11.158	9.19	9.95694702	9.9548328	10.6	2.33424001	0.53865477	10.98	8.943
7	1.58115025	1.58035277	1.6	0.98199606	0.13937792	1.854	1.301	1.55561412	1.55344324	1.55	0.9669901	0.13719366	1.826	1.281
8	16.5687848	16.5715964	16.8	1.6506316	0.35707868	17.225	15.872	17.7268789	17.6852596	17.8	3.25349809	0.62190068	19.011	16.559
9	1.21884187	1.21370055	1.2	3.37031603	0.53668593	2.293	0.126	1.22645768	1.21347999	1.2	3.42397621	0.54211729	2.313	0.122
9_B	1.44064013	1.41269902	1.4	4.15340859	0.65038572	2.748	0.102	1.45277759	1.42701752	1.4	4.13400802	0.6547403	2.767	0.103
10	4.78177583	4.77689294	4.75	1.20442219	0.17074484	5.12	4.442	5.14211391	5.14103613	5.3	1.2828688	0.23543798	5.633	4.684
11	0.88471749	0.88194575	0.88	0.40477933	0.06396829	1.013	0.757	0.79069018	0.78943429	0.8	0.36660576	0.05872106	0.91	0.674
12	10.9565246	10.9777685	11.8	3.05205271	0.67220997	12.224	9.691	11.7730575	11.7978865	12	3.94246328	0.75023357	13.292	10.348
13	17.0958507	17.1068657	17.25	1.36531704	0.20225169	17.477	16.683	18.5198355	18.4525974	18.2	2.93353726	0.62112235	19.788	17.418
13_B	5.22027852	5.21987529	5.3	1.48119567	0.25023178	5.72	4.712	5.29920229	5.29157908	5.3	1.61087786	0.26646079	5.844	4.772
14	68.9262737	68.9843092	70	6.53860795	1.60924085	71.902	65.911	72.4095808	72.2736525	73	11.0785414	2.23683689	77.031	68.207
14_B	2.38564227	2.42850767	2.7	4.86519971	0.84021438	4.028	0.717	2.1797961	2.19834469	2.7	5.05433715	0.84029446	3.881	0.524
15	2.60931596	2.60774971	2.7	1.3935389	0.21741686	3.035	2.181	2.544507	2.54351296	2.55	1.2946707	0.20977434	2.958	2.133
16	15.9175671	15.9126774	15.9	1.03927385	0.17948805	16.286	15.56	16.0529248	16.0276721	16	1.52581264	0.28041866	16.655	15.536
17	3.48890313	3.48383325	3.45	0.84103795	0.14597311	3.775	3.195	3.8644466	3.85124312	3.9	1.12315128	0.21705664	4.335	3.454
18	1.60863105	1.60968549	1.58	0.41878059	0.06987673	1.748	1.468	1.72204031	1.72407583	1.77	0.53187404	0.0876196	1.902	1.545
19	13.8746637	13.8757935	13.9	0.94984643	0.12161717	14.121	13.631	14.5986847	14.5604216	14.3	1.72340547	0.36811628	15.375	13.957
20	7.905201	7.87323866	7.8	7.03785734	1.06437263	10.005	5.755	7.84066765	7.79954779	7.8	7.09251918	1.06057794	9.94	5.699
21	2.99488083	3.00923972	3.1	2.45894309	0.39885677	3.787	2.179	3.27794222	3.2801144	3.6	2.83655461	0.45033652	4.192	2.373
22	7.55525125	7.55932663	7.6	3.39114237	0.52876393	8.609	6.485	7.89331798	7.88962604	8.2	3.74040411	0.58893087	9.104	6.723
23	21.9976445	22.0056324	22.2	2.04675625	0.32145137	22.633	21.36	22.7036922	22.6895745	22.6	2.97081012	0.5480296	23.828	21.671
24	22.8335712	22.8370231	23.2	3.18162231	0.58551943	24.036	21.696	24.6291386	24.5240648	24.6	5.54453433	0.98746269	26.714	22.792
25	5.90240581	5.90537943	6	2.49016393	0.37683863	6.659	5.149	6.35098868	6.32511086	6.4	2.82247959	0.44930311	7.31	5.481
26	12.7243461	12.717435	12.7	1.51064761	0.22220278	13.186	12.274	13.2383865	13.1871723	13.1	2.10829139	0.37608226	14.026	12.549
27	3.66908579	3.66643173	3.65	0.86857191	0.12109725	3.91	3.425	3.7468421	3.75358979	3.8	0.95362191	0.13769222	4.027	3.475

Summary of vertical slip measurements and fault slip estimates from topographic profiles extracted from LiDAR data along the Multorpor Mountain fault. Vertical offset values were analyzed using the SlipMC tool (Duckworth et al., 2021) in MATLAB, which applies Monte Carlo simulations to account for uncertainties in scarp geometry and surface correlation.